

Triple-phase-field modeling and simulation for mixed-mode fracture of bedded shale

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Abstract Comprehending the intricate mechanics and fracture characteristics of shale holds significant importance in the realm of controlling the reconstruction of shale gas reservoirs. It is noteworthy that shale typically exhibits distinctive bedding structure which sets it apart from other geological formations. Previously, single-mode cracks in shale have been widely studied by former researchers. However, its matrix and bedding may undergo various fracture modes under loading due to bedded structure. To effectively capture the mixed-mode fracture behavior observed, a triple-phase-field model is proposed in this paper. Three phase-field variables are introduced herein to track pure-tension, tensile-shear and compressive-shear cracks in the matrix and bedding, respectively. The energetic driving forces governing the propagation of pure-tension and tensile-shear cracks are formulated through the spectrum decomposition of positive strain tensor with its volumetric and deviatoric components. While the energetic driving force which propels the progression of compressive-shear cracks is derived by employing the Mohr-Coulomb criterion within the context of the negative strain

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26 tensor. For the bedding plane, lower-dimensional interfacial elements are adopted to capture
27 the mixed-mode fracture. Based on the above triple-phase-field model, both 2D and 3D
28 problems are modeled with good results. The heterogeneity of material is also considered. The
29 simulations reveal that the compression strength and fracture mode of bedded shale are
30 highly related to the orientations of the bedding plane and pre-existing fissure.

31 Keywords: Bedded shale, mixed-mode fracture, triple-phase-field model, uniaxial
32 compression, numerical simulation

33 1. Introduction

34 The study of rock damage and fracture holds considerable importance in underground
35 energy exploitation and ensuring the safety of rock engineering[1]. For example, the fracture
36 characteristics exhibited by shale play a significant role in the reconstruction of shale gas
37 reservoir, subsequently exerting a profound influence on the extraction of shale gas. The
38 bedding structure of shale, which has high compressibility and weak cementation, displays
39 noteworthy influence on the mechanical behavior and seepage properties of shale[2], and the
40 presence of which makes the fracture pattern in shale more complicated. In this context, it is
41 necessary to investigate the mixed-mode fracture mechanism of bedded shale. Numerical
42 simulation stands as an effective tool to study discontinuity problem involving both
43 mesh-based methods[3, 4] and meshless methods[5, 6].

44 In recent years, a numerical method, the phase-field method which is suitable for rock
45 fracture simulation has been favored by more and more researchers. The method uses a scalar
46 field to regularize sharp fractures, and this makes the approach more convenient and easier in

47 fracture simulation than other numerical algorithms[3, 7]. Phase-field method was originally
48 proposed only for the pure-tension (mode-I) fracture, such as three-point-bending test[1, 2],
49 Brazilian splitting test[1, 8, 9], and hydraulic fracturing[10-14] in rock engineering. However,
50 when compression load is dominant, compressive-shear fracture often occurs in rock-like
51 materials. This problem impels the enhancement of the traditional phase-field theory in order
52 to more effectively capture the mixed-mode fracture behavior. Zhang et al.[15] modified the
53 energetic driving force by considering different fracture energy release rates to capture
54 compressive-shear cracks, which was subsequently further extended by other
55 researchers[16-18]. On the other hand, in the framework of the unified phase-field theory
56 proposed by Wu[19], Wang et al.[20] and Yue et al.[21] computed the energetic driving force
57 based on maximum normal stress and maximum shear stress of material. Some of the
58 commonly used yield criteria have also been introduced into the phase-field method to derive
59 the energetic driving forces of compressive-shear crack, such as Mohr–Coulomb model[22,
60 23] and Hoek–Brown model[24].

61 Further, a dual-phase-field model was proposed to capture the cracks considering both
62 the effects of tension and compressive-shear[25, 26]. Feng and Li[27] incorporated
63 mixed-mode cohesive laws into the framework of the phase-field theory, in which a novel
64 “internal-friction-like” force was adopted to take dissipation mechanisms into account.
65 Moreover, some micromechanics-based phase-field models were proposed to simulate
66 mixed-mode fracture in geomaterials[28, 29]. These studies offer a pioneering guidance for
67 the expansion of the phase-field approach into the area of mixed-mode fracture analysis.

68 For the application of the phase-field method to bedded shale, an extension of the
69 approach is necessary to facilitate the accurate simulation of bedding fracture. The bedding
70 plane and rock matrix should be analyzed using their respective mechanics properties to
71 simulate the crack propagation in bedded shale[2, 13]. Some researchers have developed the
72 phase-field method to investigate interfacial fracture in layered structures[30-33]. On this
73 basis, Liu et al[34] further introduced a variational phase-field model for layered rocks
74 utilizing lower-dimensional interfacial element within the Finite Element Method (FEM)
75 framework, which can well capture the fracture characteristics of both the bedding plane and
76 the rock matrix. Nevertheless, the aforementioned approaches are constrained in pure-tension
77 fracture scenarios of shale and are inadequate for effectively modeling the mixed-mode
78 fracture behavior exhibited by the bedded formations.

79 To this end, this study proposes a novel triple-phase-field model (TPFM) for shale in the
80 FEM framework to simulate its mixed-mode fracture behavior with the characteristics of
81 pure-tension, tensile-shear and compressive-shear cracks considered simultaneously. The
82 lower-dimensional interfacial element assumption is also adopted similar to Liu et al[34]. The
83 accuracy of the method is tested with a 2D example of mixed-mode crack in a double-edge
84 notched concrete specimen. To examine the simulation of the effect of pre-existing fissure, a
85 2D problem of rock specimen subjected to uniaxial compression is analyzed as a benchmark
86 problem, followed by the computation of TPFM with heterogeneous material. Further, in
87 order to demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed method in the modeling of fractures in
88 shale, bedded shale and bedded shale with a pre-existing fissure subjected to uniaxial

89 compression are studied including 2D and 3D conditions.

90 2. Methodology

91 2.1 Original phase-field model

92 The phase-field method characterizes discontinuous crack with a continuous framework.
 93 For example, Fig. 1(a) shows an arbitrary body Ω with a Dirichlet boundary condition $\partial\Omega_D$, a
 94 Neumann boundary condition $\partial\Omega_N$, and discontinuous cracks Γ . $\bar{\mathbf{u}}$ denotes the specified
 95 displacement vector on boundary $\partial\Omega_D$. $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{b}}$ are the surface and body forces applied to
 96 the boundary $\partial\Omega_N$ and the entire domain, respectively. To characterize the crack, the crack
 97 surface density per unit volume γ is introduced as shown in Fig. 1(b) which is given by

$$98 \quad \gamma(\phi, \nabla\phi) = \frac{1}{2l_0}\phi^2 + \frac{l_0}{2}|\nabla\phi|^2 \quad (1)$$

99
100 *Fig. 1 Phase-field approximation for sharp cracks*

101 where l_0 is the length scale parameter to determine the visible width of the crack, and the
 102 regularization of sharp cracks uses a so-called phase-field variable $\phi(\mathbf{x}) : \Upsilon \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\Upsilon \subseteq \Omega$
 103 [35, 36]. $\phi = 0$ means no crack and $\phi = 1$ represents crack.

104 The energy required to create a smooth-diffusive fracture topology, can be approximated
 105 through substituting γ from Eq.(1) to the following integration:

106
$$\int_{\Gamma} G_c dS \approx \int_{\Gamma} G_c \gamma(\phi, \nabla \phi) dV \quad (2)$$

107 where G_c is the critical energy release rate.

108 The elastic strain energy density for an isotropic elastic body can be computed as

109
$$\psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \lambda \text{tr}^2[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] + \mu \text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2] \quad (3)$$

110 where the small strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = [\nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T]/2$ with \mathbf{u} representing displacement vector at
 111 the current time step, λ and μ are Lamé's constants, and $\text{tr}[*]$ is the trace of a matrix. The
 112 tensile (+) and compressive (-) strain energy densities are calculated using the spectral
 113 decomposition of strain tensor[35].

114
$$\psi^{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \frac{1}{2} \lambda \langle \text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] \rangle_{\pm}^2 + \mu \text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\pm}^2] \quad (4)$$

115 where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_+ = \sum_{a=1}^3 \langle \varepsilon_a \rangle_+ \mathbf{n}_a \otimes \mathbf{n}_a$ is the tensile part of strain tensor while $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_- = \sum_{a=1}^3 \langle \varepsilon_a \rangle_- \mathbf{n}_a \otimes \mathbf{n}_a$ is
 116 the compressive part, in which ε_a and \mathbf{n}_a represent the principle strains and their direction
 117 vectors, respectively. $\langle * \rangle_- = \min(*, 0)$ and $\langle * \rangle_+ = \max(*, 0)$ are the Macaulay brackets.

118 Meanwhile, tension/compression splitting of the strain energy is usually applied to prevent
 119 cracking owing to compression, and the tensile strain energy is degenerated with
 120 $\psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \phi) = g(\phi) \psi^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \psi^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$, where $g(\phi) = (1 - \phi)^2$.

121 Therefore, for a quasi-static cracking elastic body, the total energy function can be
 122 expressed as

123
$$\Pi = \int_{\Omega} [g(\phi) \psi^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) + \psi^-(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})] dV + \int_{\Gamma} G_c \gamma(\phi, \nabla \phi) dV - \int_{\Omega} \bar{\mathbf{b}} \cdot \mathbf{u} dV - \int_{\partial \Omega_N} \bar{\mathbf{f}} \cdot \mathbf{u} dS \quad (5)$$

124 Due to energy conservation, $\delta \Pi = 0$. Meanwhile, to prevent crack healing in case of
 125 decrease of $\psi^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ value, a history field is introduced as $H(\mathbf{x}, t) = \max_{0 < \tau < t} \psi^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, \tau))$. Thus,

126 the deformation and phase-field equations can be derived as follows:

$$\begin{cases}
\nabla \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{b} = 0 \\
\left(\frac{2l_0 H}{G_c} + 1\right)\phi - l_0^2 \nabla^2 \phi = \frac{2l_0 H}{G_c} \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}, \phi) = (1 - \phi)^2 \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\
\mathbf{D} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}^-}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}
\end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, \mathbf{D} is the elastic matrix, and the boundary conditions are:

$$\begin{cases}
\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{\mathbf{u}}, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_D \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{f}}, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_N \\
\nabla \phi \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0, & \text{on } \partial\Omega_N
\end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{n} denotes the unit normal vector of the Newman boundary.

The above conventional anisotropic phase-field model is only suitable for pure-tension (mode-I) fracture.

2.2. Triple-phase-field modeling for bedded shale fracture

2.2.1 Deformation and phase-field equations considering mixed-mode fracture and bedding plane

To capture different kinds of fractures, the conventional phase-field method needs to be further developed. In this study, a triple-phase-field model (TPFM) is proposed to simulate mixed-mode cracks involving pure-tension (mode I) crack, tensile-shear (mode II_t) crack as well as compressive-shear (mode II_c) crack as shown in Fig. 2(a)). Three phase-field variables ϕ_i ($i = 1, 2,$ and 3) are introduced to track the above-mentioned three types of crack propagations respectively. It should be noted that the fracture development in bedding plane requires less energy than that in the matrix. To characterize the fracture along the bedding plane, lower-dimensional interfacial element is adopted in FEM modeling along the bedding

144 plane in Fig. 2(b)[35]. The fracture surface energies in the matrix and bedded plane are
 145 respectively computed as follows:

146
 147

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of three crack modes and bedding plane in bedded shale

$$\begin{cases} \int_{\Gamma_i} G_{cI/II} dS = \int_{Y_i} G_{cI/II} \gamma(\phi_i, \nabla \phi_i) dV, & \text{for matrix fracture} \\ \int_{\Gamma_i^b} G_{cI/II}^b dS = w \int_{Y_i^b} G_{cI/II}^b \gamma^b(\phi_i, \nabla_{\tau} \phi_i) dS, & \text{for bedding fracture} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

149 where the superscript b indicates bedding plane, and w is the width of bedding plane.

150 The crack surface densities per unit volume for rock matrix and bedding plane are
 151 expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \gamma(\phi_i, \nabla \phi_i) = \frac{1}{2l_0} \phi_i^2 + \frac{l_0}{2} |\nabla \phi_i|^2, & \text{for matrix fracture} \\ \gamma^b(\phi_i, \nabla_{\tau} \phi_i) = \frac{1}{2l_0} \phi_i^2 + \frac{l_0}{2} |\nabla_{\tau} \phi_i|^2, & \text{for bedding fracture} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

153 where ∇_{τ} represents the tangential gradient operator.

154 Similar to the derivative of Eq.(6) from Eq.(5), the deformation and phase-field
 155 equations of TPFM considering bedding structure can be obtained through variational
 156 principle:

$$\begin{cases}
\nabla \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{b} = 0 \\
\left(\frac{2l_0 H}{G_c} + 1 + \frac{2l_0 H w w}{G_c^b} + w \right) \phi - l_0 \nabla^2 \phi - \frac{w l_0 \nabla^2 \phi}{\text{on } \Gamma^b} = \left(\frac{2l_0}{G_c} + \frac{2l_0 w}{G_c^b} \right) H \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}, \phi) = (1 - \phi)^2 \frac{\partial \psi^+}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \frac{\partial \psi^-}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\
\mathbf{D} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}^+}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}^-}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}
\end{cases} \quad (10)$$

2.2.2 Strain energy densities of mixed-mode fracture in rock-like material

The strain energy density, i.e. energetic driving force, of pure-tension mode, ψ_I , and that for tensile-shear crack, ψ_{II}^t , can be directly constructed by the decomposition of tensile strain energy density in Eq.(4). While the strain energy density of compressive-shear mode, ψ_{II}^c , is derived based on the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion. Thus,

$$\psi_I = \frac{\lambda}{2} \langle \text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] \rangle_+^2, \quad \psi_{II}^t = \mu \text{tr}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_+^2], \quad \text{and} \quad \psi_{II}^c = \psi_{M-C}. \quad (11)$$

where the subscript $M-C$ represents Mohr-Coulomb criterion.

The process to determine ψ_{II}^c is explained herein. Fig. 3 shows the Mohr-Coulomb criterion with linear envelopes which depends on the shear and normal stresses acting on the yield surfaces. The criterion is given by

$$|\tau| = c + \sigma_n \tan \varphi \quad (12)$$

where c is cohesion and φ is internal friction angle. σ_n is the normal stress acting on a failure surface. Note that compression is commonly taken as positive in Mohr-Coulomb model.

172
173

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion for three yield surfaces of rock-like materials

174
175

Fig. 4 Principal stress element and yield plane (compression as positive in Mohr-Coulomb model)

176 Take the plane perpendicular to the intermediate principal stress as an example (see Fig.
177 4), the normal and shear stresses on the yield plane are calculated according to the
178 equilibrium conditions.

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{13} = \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_3}{2} + \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2} \sin \varphi_{13} \\ \tau_{13} = \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3}{2} \cos \varphi_{13} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

180 In 3D condition, the other two yield surfaces can be analyzed in the same way and the
181 corresponding normal and shear stresses will be obtained similar to Eq.(13). Substituting
182 these stresses into Eq.(12), one obtains

$$\left| \frac{\sigma_i - \sigma_j}{2 \cos \varphi_{ij}} \right| = \frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{2} \tan \varphi_{ij} + c_{ij} \quad (14)$$

184 where $i < j \in [1, 2, 3]$ represents the number of principal stresses.

185 Also, according to Fig. 3, the relationship of the three internal friction angles can be

186 expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sin \varphi_{12} &= \frac{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) \sin \varphi_{13}}{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3) + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3) \sin \varphi_{13}}, \\
 \sin \varphi_{23} &= \frac{(\sigma_2 - \sigma_3) \sin \varphi_{13}}{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3) + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) \sin \varphi_{13}}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{15}$$

188 Further, when c_{13} is defined as the cohesive force of material parameter, c_{12} and c_{23} can be
 189 computed by c_{13} from Fig. 3.

$$c_{12} = c_{13} \frac{\tan \varphi_{12}}{\tan \varphi_{13}}, \quad c_{23} = c_{13} \frac{\tan \varphi_{23}}{\tan \varphi_{13}}.
 \tag{16}$$

191 To establish the energetic driving force based on the Mohr-Coulomb criterion, an over
 192 shear stress is defined as[23]

$$\Delta \tau = \langle |\tau| - \sigma_n \tan \varphi - c \rangle_+
 \tag{17}$$

194 In phase-field modeling, tension is positive. To keep the symbols consistent, the
 195 principal stress obtained above are redefined.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_1^c &= -\sigma_3^t = -\left[\lambda \langle \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- + 2\mu \langle \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- \right], \\
 \sigma_2^c &= -\sigma_2^t = -\left[\lambda \langle \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- + 2\mu \langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_- \right], \\
 \sigma_3^c &= -\sigma_1^t = -\left[\lambda \langle \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- + 2\mu \langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_- \right].
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{18}$$

197 where the superscript c represents compression to be positive, and t is the opposite.

198 Whereafter, substituting Eqs.(14) and (18) in Eq.(17), the energetic driving force based
 199 on the Mohr-Coulomb criterion is finally obtained.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi_{M-C} &= \frac{1}{2\mu} \left\langle \mu \frac{\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_- - \langle \varepsilon_3 \rangle_-}{\cos \varphi_{13}} + \left[\lambda \langle \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- + \mu (\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_- + \langle \varepsilon_3 \rangle_-) \right] \tan \varphi_{13} - c_{13} \right\rangle_+^2 \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2\mu} \left\langle \mu \frac{\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_- - \langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_-}{\cos \varphi_{23}} + \left[\lambda \langle \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- + \mu (\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_- + \langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_-) \right] \tan \varphi_{23} - c_{23} \right\rangle_+^2 \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2\mu} \left\langle \mu \frac{\langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_- - \langle \varepsilon_3 \rangle_-}{\cos \varphi_{12}} + \left[\lambda \langle \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \rangle_- + \mu (\langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_- + \langle \varepsilon_3 \rangle_-) \right] \tan \varphi_{12} - c_{12} \right\rangle_+^2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{19}$$

201 The derivation of the above equation can be found in the Annex.

202 2.2.3 Hybrid formulation of triple-phase-field model

203 To prevent crack healing under mixed-mode fracture, the driving force, also known as
 204 history field H in Eq.(10), is replaced by three new driving forces corresponding to
 205 pure-tension, tensile-shear and compressive-shear cracks respectively, namely

$$206 \quad \begin{cases} H_I(\mathbf{x}, t) = \max_{0 \leq \tau \leq t} \psi_I(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, \tau)), \\ H_{II}^t(\mathbf{x}, t) = \max_{0 \leq \tau \leq t} \psi_{II}^t(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, \tau)), \\ H_{II}^c(\mathbf{x}, t) = \max_{0 \leq \tau \leq t} \psi_{II}^c(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}, \tau)). \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

207 Thus, the governing equations of the TPFM for the simulation of mixed-mode fractures
 208 in bedded shale are obtained:

$$209 \quad \begin{cases} \nabla \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{b} = 0 \\ \left(\frac{2l_0 H_I}{G_{cI}} + 1 + \frac{2l_0 H_I w w}{G_{cI}^b} + w \right) \phi_1 - l_0 \nabla^2 \phi_1 - w l_0 \nabla^2 \phi_1 = \left(\frac{2l_0}{G_{cI}} + \frac{2l_0 w}{G_{cI}^b} \right) H_I \\ \left(\frac{2l_0 H_{II}^t}{G_{cII}} + 1 + \frac{2l_0 H_{II}^t w w}{G_{cII}^b} + w \right) \phi_2 - l_0 \nabla^2 \phi_2 - w l_0 \nabla^2 \phi_2 = \left(\frac{2l_0}{G_{cII}} + \frac{2l_0 w}{G_{cII}^b} \right) H_{II}^t \\ \left(\frac{2l_0 H_{II}^c}{G_{cII}} + 1 + \frac{2l_0 H_{II}^c w w}{G_{cII}^b} + w \right) \phi_3 - l_0 \nabla^2 \phi_3 - w l_0 \nabla^2 \phi_3 = \left(\frac{2l_0}{G_{cII}} + \frac{2l_0 w}{G_{cII}^b} \right) H_{II}^c \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} = (1 - \phi_1)^2 (1 - \phi_2)^2 (1 - \phi_3)^2 \frac{\partial \psi_0}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \\ \mathbf{D} = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

210 Note that the fifth term in Eq.(21), which is the stiffness degradation function, considers all of
 211 the three phase-field variables. Since the above formulation involves hybrid conditions, it can
 212 be called the hybrid formulation[37] of TPFM. Although Eq.(21) does not strictly satisfy the
 213 variational principle, it is capable of mixed-mode fracture analysis.

214 3. Numerical implementation and model verification

215 3.1 FEM discretization

216 The TPFM governing equations are discretized to be applied in FEM framework. Firstly,
 217 the weak form equations of the deformation equation and three phase-field diffusion equations
 218 with the lower-dimensional interfacial element in FEM framework are derived and presented
 219 in sequence below.

$$220 \quad \int_{\Omega} (-\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} (\bar{\mathbf{b}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}) d\Omega + \int_{\partial \Omega} (\bar{\mathbf{f}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}) dS = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$221 \quad \int_{\Omega} -2H_I (1 - \phi_1) \delta \phi_1 dV + \int_{\Gamma} G_{cI} \left(l_0 \nabla \phi_1 \cdot \nabla \delta \phi_1 + \frac{1}{l_0} \phi_1 \delta \phi_1 \right) dV -$$

$$\int_{\Gamma^b} 2wH_I (1 - \phi_1) \delta \phi_1 dS + \int_{\Gamma^b} G_{cI}^b w \left(l_0 \nabla_{\tau} \phi_1 \cdot \nabla_{\tau} \delta \phi_1 + \frac{1}{l_0} \phi_1 \delta \phi_1 \right) dS = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$222 \quad \int_{\Omega} -2H_{II}^I (1 - \phi_2) \delta \phi_2 dV + \int_{\Gamma} G_{cII} \left(l_0 \nabla \phi_2 \cdot \nabla \delta \phi_2 + \frac{1}{l_0} \phi_2 \delta \phi_2 \right) dV -$$

$$\int_{\Gamma^b} 2wH_{II}^I (1 - \phi_2) \delta \phi_2 dS + \int_{\Gamma^b} G_{cII}^b w \left(l_0 \nabla_{\tau} \phi_2 \cdot \nabla_{\tau} \delta \phi_2 + \frac{1}{l_0} \phi_2 \delta \phi_2 \right) dS = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$223 \quad \int_{\Omega} -2H_{II}^c (1 - \phi_3) \delta \phi_3 dV + \int_{\Gamma} G_{cII} \left(l_0 \nabla \phi_3 \cdot \nabla \delta \phi_3 + \frac{1}{l_0} \phi_3 \delta \phi_3 \right) dV -$$

$$\int_{\Gamma^b} 2wH_{II}^c (1 - \phi_3) \delta \phi_3 dS + \int_{\Gamma^b} G_{cII}^b w \left(l_0 \nabla_{\tau} \phi_3 \cdot \nabla_{\tau} \delta \phi_3 + \frac{1}{l_0} \phi_3 \delta \phi_3 \right) dS = 0 \quad (25)$$

224 The nodal values of \mathbf{u} , ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , and ϕ_3 are represented by the standard vector-matrix
 225 notation. Therefore, their discretization can be expressed as follows:

$$226 \quad \mathbf{u} = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{N}_u \mathbf{u}^e, \quad \phi_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \phi_{1i} = \mathbf{N}_{\phi_1} \boldsymbol{\phi}_1^e,$$

$$\phi_2 = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \phi_{2i} = \mathbf{N}_{\phi_2} \boldsymbol{\phi}_2^e, \quad \phi_3 = \sum_{i=1}^n N_i \phi_{3i} = \mathbf{N}_{\phi_3} \boldsymbol{\phi}_3^e. \quad (26)$$

227 where N_i is the shape function at node i , and n is the number of nodes per element.

228 The gradients of nodal values of \mathbf{u} , ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , and ϕ_3 can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\varepsilon &= \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{B}_i^u \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{B}_u \mathbf{u}^e, \\
\nabla \phi_1 &= \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{B}_i^{\phi_1} \phi_{1i} = \mathbf{B}_{\phi_1} \phi_1^e, \quad \nabla_{\tau} \phi_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{B}_{\tau i}^{\phi_1} \phi_{1i} = \mathbf{B}_{\tau \phi_1} \phi_1^e \\
\nabla \phi_2 &= \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{B}_i^{\phi_2} \phi_{2i} = \mathbf{B}_{\phi_2} \phi_2^e, \quad \nabla_{\tau} \phi_2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{B}_{\tau i}^{\phi_2} \phi_{2i} = \mathbf{B}_{\tau \phi_2} \phi_2^e, \\
\nabla \phi_3 &= \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{B}_i^{\phi_3} \phi_{3i} = \mathbf{B}_{\phi_3} \phi_3^e, \quad \nabla_{\tau} \phi_3 = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{A}_{\tau i}^{\phi_3} \phi_{3i} = \mathbf{B}_{\tau \phi_3} \phi_3^e
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

230 where \mathbf{B}_u and \mathbf{B}_{ϕ} represent the derivatives of the shape functions for the deformation and
231 phase fields, respectively, and $\mathbf{B}_{\tau \phi}$ is the tangential derivative of the shape function. They
232 are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{B}_i^u &= \begin{bmatrix} N_{i,x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N_{i,y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_{i,z} \\ N_{i,y} & N_{i,x} & 0 \\ 0 & N_{i,z} & N_{i,y} \\ N_{i,z} & 0 & N_{i,x} \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{B}_i^{\phi_1} = \mathbf{B}_i^{\phi_2} = \mathbf{B}_i^{\phi_3} &= \begin{bmatrix} N_{i,x} \\ N_{i,y} \\ N_{i,z} \end{bmatrix}, \\
\mathbf{B}_{\tau i}^{\phi_1} = \mathbf{B}_{\tau i}^{\phi_2} = \mathbf{B}_{\tau i}^{\phi_3} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1-n_1^2 & -n_1 n_2 & -n_1 n_3 \\ -n_2 n_1 & 1-n_2^2 & -n_2 n_3 \\ -n_3 n_1 & -n_3 n_2 & 1-n_3^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N_{i,x} \\ N_{i,y} \\ N_{i,z} \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

234 where n_1 , n_2 , and n_3 are the three components of the unit normal vector of the bedding plane,
235 By substituting the above space discretization terms into Eqs.(22)-(25) and considering
236 the arbitrary test functions, the final FEM discretization form for all equations are obtained as
237 follows:

238

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_u & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{K}_{\phi_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{K}_{\phi_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{K}_{\phi_3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}^e \\ \boldsymbol{\phi}_1^e \\ \boldsymbol{\phi}_2^e \\ \boldsymbol{\phi}_3^e \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_u \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi_1} \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi_2} \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi_3} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_u \\ \mathbf{R}_{\phi_1} \\ \mathbf{R}_{\phi_2} \\ \mathbf{R}_{\phi_3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

239

where \mathbf{R}_u , \mathbf{R}_{ϕ_1} , \mathbf{R}_{ϕ_2} , and \mathbf{R}_{ϕ_3} are the residuals of the four discrete equations, and the

240

stiffness matrices \mathbf{K} and external force matrices \mathbf{F} for deformation and three phase fields

241

are expressed in sequence as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}_u &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{B}_u^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B}_u dV, \\ \mathbf{F}_u &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Omega} (\mathbf{N}_u^T \bar{\mathbf{b}}) dV + \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_s'} \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbf{N}_u^T \bar{\mathbf{f}}) dS \\ \mathbf{K}_{\phi_1} &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Gamma} \left[\mathbf{N}_{\phi_1}^T (2H_I + G_{cI}/l_0) \mathbf{N}_{\phi_1} + \mathbf{B}_{\phi_1}^T G_{cI} l_0 \mathbf{B}_{\phi_1} \right] dV + \\ &\quad \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_b'} \int_{\Gamma^b} \left[\mathbf{N}_{\phi_1}^T (2H_I + G_{cI}^b/l_0) \mathbf{N}_{\phi_1} + \mathbf{B}_{\tau\phi_1}^T G_{cI}^b l_0 \mathbf{B}_{\tau\phi_1} \right] dS \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi_1} &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Gamma} 2H_I \mathbf{N}_{\phi_1}^T dV + \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_b'} \int_{\Gamma^b} 2wH_I \mathbf{N}_{\phi_1}^T dS \\ \mathbf{K}_{\phi_2} &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Gamma} \left[\mathbf{N}_{\phi_2}^T (2H_{II} + G_{cII}/l_0) \mathbf{N}_{\phi_2} + \mathbf{B}_{\phi_2}^T G_{cII} l_0 \mathbf{B}_{\phi_2} \right] dV + \\ &\quad \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_b'} \int_{\Gamma^b} \left[\mathbf{N}_{\phi_2}^T (2H_{II} + G_{cII}^b/l_0) \mathbf{N}_{\phi_2} + \mathbf{B}_{\tau\phi_2}^T G_{cII}^b l_0 \mathbf{B}_{\tau\phi_2} \right] dS \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi_2} &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Gamma} 2H_{II} \mathbf{N}_{\phi_2}^T dV + \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_b'} \int_{\Gamma^b} 2wH_{II} \mathbf{N}_{\phi_2}^T dS \\ \mathbf{K}_{\phi_3} &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Gamma} \left[\mathbf{N}_{\phi_3}^T (2H_{II}^c + G_{cII}/l_0) \mathbf{N}_{\phi_3} + \mathbf{B}_{\phi_3}^T G_{cII} l_0 \mathbf{B}_{\phi_3} \right] dV + \\ &\quad \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_b'} \int_{\Gamma^b} \left[\mathbf{N}_{\phi_3}^T (2H_{II}^c + G_{cII}^b/l_0) \mathbf{N}_{\phi_3} + \mathbf{B}_{\tau\phi_3}^T G_{cII}^b l_0 \mathbf{B}_{\tau\phi_3} \right] dS \\ \mathbf{F}_{\phi_3} &= \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Gamma} 2H_{II}^c \mathbf{N}_{\phi_3}^T dV + \mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_b'} \int_{\Gamma^b} 2wH_{II}^c \mathbf{N}_{\phi_3}^T dS \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

243

where $\mathbf{A}_{e=1}^{N_e}$ denotes matrix assembly from element level to global level, N_e is the total

244

number of elements, N_s' is the number of surface elements, and N_b' is the number of

245 lower-dimensional bedding elements. Using the finite element formulations derived and
 246 presented in Eq.(30), four partial differential equations in Eq.(21) involving a deformation
 247 equation and three phase-field diffusion equations can be solved.

248 3.2 Numerical implementation

249 In this study, a powerful FEM-based software, COMSOL Multiphysics, is employed to
 250 obtain numerical solutions. To improve the convergence of the model, a separated coupling
 251 solver based on staggered strategy is applied. The implicit generalized- α method is adopted as
 252 the time stepping method. The three history fields in Eq.(20) are tracked using three State
 253 Variables in the software[38]. The progressing flowchart of TPFM for mixed-mode fracture of
 254 bedded shale is presented with implementation details in Table 1.

255 *Table 1 Flowchart of TPFM for the mixed-mode fracture of bedded shale*

Initiation

$$\mathbf{u}_0, (H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_0 \text{ and } (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_0$$

For each successive time step $i+1$ do

$$\mathbf{u}_i, (H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_i \text{ and } (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_i \text{ are known}$$

Initiation

$$\text{Construct the initial guess } (\mathbf{u})_{i+1}^{j=0}, (H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_{i+1}^{j=0} \text{ and } (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_{i+1}^{j=0}$$

For each successive iteration step $j+1$ do

$$(\mathbf{u})_i^j, (H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_i^j \text{ and } (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_i^j \text{ are known}$$

Newton-Raphson iterative solution scheme

1. Solve Eq.(29)₁ using $(\mathbf{u})_{i+1}^j, (H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_{i+1}^j$ and $(\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_{i+1}^j$
 2. Update $(H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_{i+1}^{j+1}$ using $(\mathbf{u})_{i+1}^j$ and $(H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_{i+1}^j$
 3. Solve Eq.(29)₂₋₄ using $(\mathbf{u})_{i+1}^{j+1}, (H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c)_{i+1}^{j+1}$ and $(\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_{i+1}^j$
 4. Evaluate the total relative error between $(\mathbf{u}, H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c, \phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_{i+1}^j$
-

and $(\mathbf{u}, H_I, H_{II}^t, H_{II}^c, \phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3)_{i+1}^{j+1}$

until the tolerance $< \varepsilon_r = 1 \times 10^{-6}$

End

256 3.3. Model verification

257 3.3.1. Mixed-mode crack in double-edge notched concrete specimen

258 This section numerically simulates a classical benchmark test problem of a 2D concrete
259 specimen with mixed-mode fracture as shown in Fig. 5, which was initially experimentally
260 studied by Nooru-Mohamed[39]. It is selected due to its correspondence with a range of tests
261 conducted under non-proportional loading scenarios showing bending cracks with diverse
262 curvatures[40]. The double-sided cut concrete specimen measures $200 \times 200 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$ and
263 features two incisions with dimensions of $25 \times 5 \times 50 \text{ mm}^3$ in the middle of both the left and
264 right sides. The specimen is affixed to a specialized rigid steel frame enabling the application
265 of diverse shear and tension loading conditions under precise force or displacement control. To
266 elaborate, normal displacement is restricted along the lower-right and bottom boundaries.
267 Meanwhile, the upper-left boundary maintains a constant shear force \bar{f} , and a normal
268 displacement \bar{u} is applied at the top.

269 Herein, three specimens, i.e. DENS-4a, DENS-4b, and DENS-4c, are analyzed[27, 40]
270 with the same numerical parameters: Young's modulus $E = 30 \text{ GPa}$, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.2$,
271 $G_{cII} = 10G_{cI} = 250 \text{ N/m}$, $\varphi_{13} = 30^\circ$, and $l_0 = 2 \text{ mm}$. Different shear forces of
272 $\bar{f} = 5, 10, \text{ and } 27.5 \text{ kN}$ are assigned to the specimens, respectively. In the FEM analysis, the
273 computational domain is discretized uniformly with quadrilateral elements in the size of
274 $h = 0.5 \text{ mm}$. The displacement increment is fixed as $\Delta u = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}$ for each time step. In

275 Fig. 6, a comparison is presented between the numerical and experimental results, where the
 276 three phase-fields variables are integrated through $1 - \sqrt[3]{(1 - \phi_1)(1 - \phi_2)(1 - \phi_3)}$ to depict
 277 mixed-mode fracture. It is evident that the simulated phase-field crack paths agree well with
 278 those observed in the experiment, confirming the precision and validity of the proposed model.

279
 280 Fig. 5 Geometry and boundary conditions of double-edge notched concrete specimen (unit: mm)

281
 282 (a) Crack patterns observed in experiments from Nooru-Mohamed [39]

283
 284 (b) Crack patterns obtained by the proposed TPFM

285 Fig. 6 Comparison of experimental and numerical results

286 3.3.2. Rock specimen with pre-existing fissure under uniaxial compression

287 To demonstrate the ability of TPFM in capturing cracks in rock-like materials under
 288 uniaxial compression, a 2D rectangular rock specimen with an inclined flaw in the middle is
 289 studied. Both experimental and numerical investigations have been conducted for this

290 problem previously[25, 26, 41, 42]. The geometry and boundary conditions are illustrated in
 291 Fig. 7(a), with a centrally positioned pre-existing fissure measuring 15 mm in length and 0.5
 292 mm in width. Fig. 7(b) shows the typical crack modes of rock-like materials with a
 293 pre-existing fissure subjected to uniaxial compression[43]. Following a former study[26], the
 294 basic parameters are set as follows: $E = 32.6 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.21$, $G_{cI} = 16 \text{ N/m}$,
 295 $G_{cII} = 200 \text{ N/m}$, $c_{13} = 500 \text{ kPa}$, and $l_0 = 1 \text{ mm}$. Considering the existence of the fissure,
 296 this computation uses free triangular mesh with maximum characteristics size of
 297 $h = 0.5 \text{ mm}$. At every time step, a displacement increment of $\Delta u = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}$ is applied.
 298 The internal friction angle, ϕ_{13} , ranges from 20° to 35° , while the remaining internal friction
 299 angles are determined according to Eq.(15). The simulation results are shown in Fig. 8. Fig.
 300 8(a) illustrates that as the internal friction angle increases, the phase-field cracks exhibit
 301 varying propagation paths, and the proposed model effectively captures wing cracks, coplanar
 302 secondary cracks, and oblique secondary cracks. As shown in Fig. 8(b), the compression
 303 strength of the specimen exhibits a significant increase as the internal friction angle ϕ_{13} rises.
 304 This suggests that rock specimens with higher internal friction angles require greater
 305 compressive loads to induce failure.

306

307 Fig. 7 (a) Geometry and boundary conditions of rock specimen with pre-existing fissure under uniaxial compression (left)
 308 (b) Typical crack pattern in rock-like material with a pre-existing fissure under uniaxial compression (right)

309
310

(a) final phase-field cracks

311
312

(b) stress- strain curves

313 Fig. 8 Numerical simulation results by the proposed TPFM with different internal friction angle

314 4. Numerical examples

315 Using the proposed model, this section investigates the failure characteristics of shale
 316 specimens under uniaxial compression. These categories encompass bedded shale and bedded
 317 shale featuring a pre-existing fissure. The cases in this section adopt the same basic
 318 parameters: $E = 30 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.25$, $l_0 = 1 \text{ mm}$, $c_{13} = 5 \text{ MPa}$, $\varphi_{13} = 30^\circ$,
 319 $G_{cII} = 5G_{cI} = 500 \text{ N/m}$, $G_{cI}^b = G_{cI}/10$, and $G_{cII}^b = G_{cII}/10$, and the displacement increment
 320 remains constant at $\Delta u = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}$ for each time step. In such cases, free triangular
 321 elements (2D) and tetrahedral elements (3D) are employed, and the mesh strategies are
 322 determined based on the inclinations of the bedding planes and pre-existing fissures.

323 4.1 Bedded shale under uniaxial compression

324 The bedding planes, being a weak layer structure, exert a considerable influence on the
325 mechanical properties of shale formations. Heng et al.[44] conducted experimental
326 investigations on the fracture patterns of bedded shale under uniaxial compression. This
327 section presents the results of 3D and 2D numerical simulations studying the impact of
328 bedding structure on the strength characteristics, mechanical properties, and anisotropy of
329 fracture modes in shale. Various bedding angles are applied to bedded shale samples under
330 uniaxial compression, and the solutions are compared with aforementioned experimental
331 results.

332 In the experiment, to prepare shale specimens with varying bedding angles, core samples
333 were extracted with drilling directions perpendicular to the bedding surface, resulting in
334 angles of $\alpha = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ,$ and $90^\circ,$ respectively, as shown in Fig. 9(a). The processed
335 cylinder specimens have dimensions of 50 mm in diameter and 100 mm in height.
336 Irrespective of the bedding angle, the initial spacings between bedding layers are constant at
337 12.5 mm. Fig. 9(b) illustrates the geometry and boundaries of the bedded shale during
338 experiment and takes the 30° bedding angle as an example. Fig. 10, sourced from
339 reference[44] where the failure process and fracture morphology are discussed, displays the
340 experimental results for the fracture patterns of bedded shale with varying bedding angles.

341

342

Fig. 9 (a) Directional coring diagram of shale specimen, (b) geometry and boundary conditions for bedded shale

343

344

Fig. 10 Failure pattern of bedded shale subjected to uniaxial compression[44]

345

In TPFM analysis, the material with homogeneous Young's modulus is first analyzed.

346

3D models are simulated using free tetrahedral element with the maximum mesh size of

347

$h = 2\ell_0$ to optimize computational efficiency, resulting in a total number of approximately

348

400,000 elements. Thereafter, 2D models are calculated using about 50,000 free triangular

349

elements with the maximum element characteristic size being not larger than $l_0/2$. Due to

350

the lower-dimensional modeling of bedding plane, the number of elements in different

351

models can be slightly different owing to varying bedding angles (Fig. 9).

352

The 3D and 2D crack results are presented in Fig. 11(a) and (b), respectively, which

353

effectively capture the crack path in both the bedding plane and matrix. Shear cracks along

354

the bedding plane become particularly prominent, especially when the bedding angle is 30° .

355

Nonetheless, the outcomes exhibit slight disparities when compared to the experimental

356

findings in Fig. 10. This variance can be attributed to the inherent friction that arises between

357 the two ends of the testing machine and the specimens during the experimental procedure,
358 consequently influencing the failure patterns. Additionally, it is essential to acknowledge the
359 inherent randomness associated with experiments, thus, a single set of experiments may not
360 comprehensively elucidate the entirety of the failure behavior. The variance between the 3D
361 and 2D simulation results is due to two primary factors. Firstly, to optimize computational
362 efficiency, the 3D model employs a mesh with a larger maximum characteristic size
363 compared to the 2D model, which serves as a significant contributing factor. Secondly, the
364 inherent differences in dimension reduction methods also contribute to this distinction.
365 Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the results from the 3D and 2D models exhibit a high
366 degree of similarity, as depicted in Fig. 11(a) and (b). Consequently, for subsequent
367 simulation procedures, the 2D model is chosen for its simplicity and efficiency. Furthermore,
368 Fig. 11(c) illustrates that once a shear crack coalesces, the displacement field experiences
369 discontinuity across the crack, ultimately leading to frictional sliding.

370
371

(a) final phase-field cracks of 3D homogeneous model

(b) final phase-field cracks of 2D homogeneous model

(c) final vertical displacements of 2D homogeneous model (displacements scaled by 5)

Fig. 11 Bedded shale specimen with homogenous Young's modulus

372
373

374
375
376

377 Crack initiation within the homogeneous bedded shale specimen is primarily triggered by
378 the presence of a weak bedding plane. It is worth noting that both the shale matrix and bedding
379 plane possess varying mechanical properties. Hence, a heterogeneous Young's modulus
380 following Weibull distribution is assigned to the bedded shale specimen. This allows this
381 research to investigate the impact of randomness on the failure morphology of bedded shale.
382 Specifically, two heterogeneous fields are generated while keeping the random parameters
383 constant. Fig. 12 shows the final phase-field crack patterns of shale specimens with different
384 bedding angles, incorporating random variations in Young's modulus. As anticipated, the final
385 failure mode exhibits increased complexity compared to specimens with uniform Young's
386 modulus. The location of crack initiation, influenced by both the presence of a weak bedding
387 plane and heterogeneous Young's modulus, displays greater uncertainty. In summary, the

388 numerical simulations reveal mixed-mode fractures in specimens with varying bedding angles,
389 consistent with the experimental observations in Fig. 10.

390
391

(a) final phase-field cracks of 2D heterogeneous model I

392
393
394

(b) final phase-field cracks of 2D heterogeneous model II

Fig. 12 Final phase-field crack of bedded shales with different bedding angle

Fig. 13 Stress-strain curves of bedded shale subjected to uniaxial compression

395
396

397 Both the homogeneous and heterogeneous models exhibit distinct brittle fracture
 398 characteristics, as evidenced by the stress-strain curves presented in Fig. 13. Notably, the
 399 stress-strain curve of the 3D model displays a noticeable softening stage before reaching the
 400 peak stress, attributable to the larger mesh size employed in the model. Consequently, the
 401 peak stress is reduced. Moreover, the divergence in bedding angle leads to different failure
 402 modes in shale specimens. Transitioning from Fig. 13(a) to (d), it is evident that the
 403 compression strength of shale specimens with bedding angles of 0° and 90° is significantly
 404 higher than that of specimens with bedding angles of 30° and 60° . The introduction of
 405 heterogeneous Young's modulus results in an overall reduction in the compression strength of
 406 bedded shale. In summary, the compression strengths of bedded shale specimens with varying

407 bedding angles exhibit a U-shaped trend, with higher values at both extremes and lower
 408 values in the middle, as depicted in Fig. 14. This trend is in substantial agreement with the
 409 experimental findings[44].

410
 411 *Fig. 14 Relationship between compression strength and bedding angle α*

4.2 Bedded shale with pre-existing fissure under uniaxial compression

413 Having demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed TPFM, this study now aims to
 414 address more intricate and challenging problems. The interaction between pre-existing
 415 fissures and bedding planes is pivotal in understanding the bedded shale failure mechanisms.
 416 Consequently, this section delves into the failure behavior of bedded shale specimens
 417 featuring a central pre-existing fissure measuring 15 mm in length and 0.5 mm in width,
 418 subjected to uniaxial compression. A total of 16 models are analyzed which are categorized
 419 into four groups, with each group maintaining a constant bedding angle, i.e. $\alpha = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ,$
 420 and 90° , respectively. Each group involves four pre-existing fissure angles, $\beta = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ$
 421 and 90° . Fig. 15 presents the schematic diagram of the problem.

Fig. 15 Geometry and boundary conditions for bedded shale with inclined flaw

422
423

424 In Fig. 16(a), the final crack pattern corresponding to various fissure angles at a bedding
 425 angle of 0° is presented. Evidently, crack propagation along the bedding plane is a common
 426 occurrence. When β equals 0° , the phase-field crack forms a closed hexagonal ring encircling
 427 the pre-existing fissure. Subsequently, shear slip cracks originate from the upper-left and right
 428 corners of the hexagonal ring, leading to a loss of specimen carrying capacity. At $\beta = 30^\circ$,
 429 cracking initiates from the tips of the pre-existing fissure, creating a primary crack path along
 430 the fissure's orientation, accompanied by secondary cracks along the bedding plane. With $\beta =$
 431 60° , cracking still commences from the fissure tips, resulting in two main cracks, one
 432 exhibiting mode-I behavior and the other mode-II, similar to Fig. 8. At $\beta = 90^\circ$, splitting
 433 along the intermediate bedding plane takes place initially. As it progresses, compressive-shear
 434 cracks initiate and propagate along the fissure's tips until the specimen's bearing capacity is
 435 lost. The orientations of the shear cracks resemble those at $\beta = 60^\circ$. Notably, the peak load at
 436 $\beta = 0^\circ$ is considerably higher than in the other cases. Additionally, at $\beta = 30^\circ, 60^\circ,$ and 90° ,
 437 the post-peak stages of the stress-strain curves exhibit noticeable bending due to the transition
 438 from mode-I to mode-II crack behavior.

439

440

441

442

Fig. 16 Final phase-field crack and stress-strain curves of bedded shale specimen with varying bedding angle and pre-existing fissure angles

443

As shown in Fig. 16(b), with a bedding angle of 30° , the first three models ($\beta = 0^\circ, 30^\circ,$

444

and 60°) present primary compressive-shear cracks along a bedding plane interacting with the

445

pre-existing fissure. The only discernible distinction lies in the precise crack initiation

446

locations, which vary slightly. Conversely, when β equals 90° , the ultimate crack pattern

447

becomes intricate, encompassing both shear and tensile cracks within the matrix and the

448

bedding simultaneously. The bedding planes closest to either side of the pre-existing fissure

449

eventually undergo shear slip, with the two shear cracks intersecting. Fig. 16 (b) illustrates a

450

gradual reduction in peak load as β changes, with the order being $0^\circ, 90^\circ, 60^\circ,$ and $30^\circ,$

451

respectively. Fig. 16(c) shows that under a bedding angle of 60° , the varying pre-existing

452 fissure angle results in markedly different fracture patterns. At $\beta = 0^\circ$, it is surprising to note
453 that crack initiation does not originate from the pre-existing fissure. Instead, the primary
454 failure mode involves shear slip along the bedding plane, closely resembling the behavior of
455 specimens without a pre-existing fissure, as seen in Fig. 11. This suggests that the impact of a
456 pre-existing fissure on crack initiation and propagation is negligible when β equals 0° .
457 Furthermore, at $\beta = 30^\circ$, 60° , and 90° , cracks initiate from the tips of the pre-existing fissure,
458 leading to more complex final crack patterns. Both mode-I and mode-II cracks are observed
459 within the shale matrix and bedding plane simultaneously. Examining the stress-strain curves
460 (Fig. 16(c)), it is evident that the peak load decreases as the inclination angle of the
461 pre-existing fissure increases, contrary to the trend observed in Fig. 16(b). This suggests that
462 the interaction between the bedding plane and pre-existing fissure can alter the compressive
463 strength of bedded shale. Fig. 16(d) illustrates the final crack patterns of specimens with
464 varying pre-existing fissure angles under a bedding angle of 90° . When β equals 0° , the crack
465 pattern takes on an X-shaped configuration, consisting entirely of compressive-shear cracks
466 extending across the bedding plane. This aligns with the findings of Zhou et al.[22] when
467 simulating rock-like materials lacking a bedding structure. At $\beta = 30^\circ$, cracking initiates from
468 the pre-existing fissure tips, resulting in two distinct mode-I and mode-II cracks along an
469 antisymmetric direction, akin to Fig. 8. Notably, there are noticeable secondary cracks
470 propagating along the bedding plane. With $\beta = 60^\circ$, the crack also originates from the
471 pre-existing fissure tips, yielding two primary cracks along the fissure's orientation,
472 accompanied by a variety of secondary cracks. However, a significant split occurs down the

473 middle of the specimen, and the crack crosses the bedding plane when the pre-existing
474 fissure's inclination angle matches that of the bedding. Subsequently, a compressive-shear
475 crack initiates from the fissure tips and extends along the upper-left and lower-right
476 directions until it penetrates the specimen. Fig. 16(d) demonstrates that the specimen attains
477 its highest peak load at $\beta = 0^\circ$. Another noteworthy distinction is the slight fluctuation
478 observed in the post-peak stages of the stress-strain curves, resulting from changes in the
479 fracture mode when $\beta = 30^\circ$, 60° , and 90° .

480 5. Conclusions

481 This paper proposes a novel triple-phase-field model (TPFM) designed to effectively
482 capture mixed-mode fracture behavior in rock-like materials. Additionally, the method
483 considers the mixed-mode fracture characteristics of shale bedding structures by employing a
484 lower-dimensional interfacial element assumption within the FEM framework. This approach
485 constructs the energetic driving force for compressive-shear cracks based on the
486 Mohr-Coulomb criterion in three dimensions, accounting for variations in the two friction
487 angles and cohesion forces as principal stresses evolve during the cracking process. Utilizing
488 this model, this paper conducts an investigation into the failure characteristics of bedded
489 shale subjected to uniaxial compression. This study demonstrates that the proposed TPFM
490 qualitatively captures mixed-mode fractures in bedded shale, encompassing both bedding and
491 matrix regions. Specifically, when the bedding direction aligns with or is perpendicular to the
492 loading direction, the shale specimen exhibits higher compression strength. However, at
493 angles of 30° and 60° between the two directions, shear slip along the bedding plane

494 significantly reduces the shale specimen's compression strength. Moreover, the interaction
495 between the bedding plane and pre-existing fissures can induce various fracture modes and
496 alter the compression strength of bedded shale. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that there is
497 need for further adjustments to model parameters based on experimental data to enhance the
498 model's ability to simulate practical engineering scenarios.
499

500

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506

507 [Data Availability Statement](#)

508 Some or all data, models, or code generated or used during the study are available from the
509 corresponding author by request.

510

511 [Conflict of Interest](#)

512 The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this paper.

513

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515

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